

Deliverable 3.4
Inclusivity Footprint Calculator

30 April 2025

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*Legend = **R** – Report // **DEM** – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs // **DEC** – Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc. // **DMP** – Data management plan // **OTHER** – Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

	Name of the Entity	Acronym	Role	Country	ORG Type
1	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna	UNIBO	CO	IT	RTD
2	Universidade do Porto	U. PORTO	BE	PT	RTD
3	Association Européenne pour la Démocratie Locale	ALDA	BE	FR	NGO
4	WeDo Project Intelligence Made Easy SL	WeDo	BE	ES	SME
5	Aalborg Universitet	AAU	BE	DK	RTD
6	Turun Yliopisto	UTU	BE	FI	RTD
7	Universitaet Innsbruck	UIBK	BE	AT	RTD
8	Université de Genève	UNIGE	AP	CH	RTD
9	The University of Manchester	UNIMAN	AP	UK	RTD

*Legend = Role in the Project: C – Coordinator // B – Beneficiary // AP – Associated Partner // Organization Type: RTD – Research and Technological Development// PHI – Public Health Institution // Hosp – Hospital // SME – Small and medium-sized enterprises. // LC – Large Company // NGO – Non-Governmental Org.

Table 1. The SINCRONY Consortium

	Work Packages Name	WP Leader
WP1	Coordination and Management	UNIBO
WP2	Co-Design	UNIBO
WP3	Assessment of existing practices in an intersectional lens	UTU
WP4	Power-based analysis of social narratives and experiences	UNIGE
WP5	Piloting enhancement and innovation pathways	ALDA
WP6	Evaluation	U. PORTO
WP7	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation, and Impact	WeDo

Table 2. The SINCRONY Work Packages

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Executive summary

This technical report presents the contents and technical description of the Inclusivity Footprint Calculator, a tool developed within the SINCRONY project as part of Task 3.4 *Overall integration of recommendations for best inclusive practices in an intersectional lens*. The calculator is a web application designed to benchmark inclusivity in various participatory and deliberative practices that engage young people. It comprises a total of 34 questions, structured into five sections derived from SINCRONY D3.3 *Integration of Critical Assessment of Practices*. These sections are: Inclusion, Youth Voice and Power, Critical Awareness, Recognition, and Impact. Users can choose to benchmark specific sections or all five of them. After answering all questions in the selected sections, users receive an overall inclusivity score, based on their answers, and individual inclusivity scores for each section they have benchmarked. Users also receive recommendations based on existing good practices at different levels of governance, society, and communities. Within the SINCRONY project, the calculator will be used in WP5 *Piloting enhancement and innovation pathways*. It will also be openly available for public use.

1 Objective of the calculator

What is this calculator?

The inclusivity footprint calculator is a calculator for benchmarking inclusivity in existing participatory and deliberative practices that engage young people. The calculator compares user inputs to an “ideal case” for inclusivity and intersectionality, and provides an inclusivity score and recommendations for improvement. Scholarly work on intersectionality and deliberation has guided the creation of the calculator.

Why this calculator?

The inclusivity footprint calculator was created in the framework of the SINCRONY project as a tool to assess or benchmark existing participatory and deliberative practices working with youth civic engagement.

The calculator serves as a benchmarking tool but also has an important educational function. Grounded in an intersectional lens, the tool acknowledges inclusivity as a dynamic process of learning and betterment.

The calculator is meant for organisations, communities, and schools working with participatory and deliberative practices that engage young people. Users can utilise the recommendations from the calculator to improve the participatory and deliberative practices in their work.

Existing references

The process of designing and building the calculator started with getting inspiration from existing calculators. A model was taken mainly from CO2 calculators, as these calculators are widely known and represent established tools. The inclusivity footprint calculator was inspired by the user experience of [WWF's footprint calculator](#) and [Sitra's lifestyle calculator](#), where users are given clear questions and provided with not only a calculation of their CO2 level but recommendations and information to reduce their emissions. The modern design of both WWF's and Sitra's calculators also served as an inspiration for the design of the inclusivity footprint calculator.

Despite inspiration, the inclusivity footprint calculator's operation was built from scratch by the responsible research team. Since inclusivity is not a similarly concrete phenomenon as CO2 emissions, there were no calculations or databases that could have been directly utilised. Instead, the logic of the calculator, i.e., how it works, was built by the researchers based on the previous work carried out in the SINCRONY project WP3 and the deliverables D3.1 *Assessment of EU-level deliberative and participatory practices through an intersectional lens*, D3.2 *Assessment of national and local practices*, and D3.3 *Integration of Critical Assessment of Practices*. Additionally, since D3.1 was inspired by WP2 deliverable D2.1 *Literature review and knowledge integration report*, the contents of the inclusivity calculator are also inspired by the theoretical discussions around the concept of intersectionality. The building of the calculator thus captures the circular logic of the SINCRONY project, with its different parts feeding into each other. The circular logic will be further achieved once the calculator is used in the project's pilot phase.

The logic and operation of the calculator are described in section three of this report.

User value

The calculator’s most substantial value for its users is the educational function of the calculator. **Users will receive recommendations based on existing good practices at different levels of governance, society, and communities.** The recommendations give the users the opportunity to improve their existing participatory and deliberative practices and critically weigh in on their actions. The calculator can operate in different contexts and can be helpful for practices done in schools, organisations, communities, or projects.

2 Contents

The calculator questions are structured under five sections derived from SINCRONY’s D3.3 (and originally, D3.1 and D3.2). These sections are Inclusion, Youth Voice and Power, Critical Awareness, Recognition and Impact. These are all important parts of furthering inclusivity and the impact of youth participation. The sections and what they benchmark are described in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The sections of the calculator

<p style="text-align: center;">Inclusion</p> <p>This section benchmarks recruitment practices, proactive outreach, accessibility, how participants are made to feel they belong, and support mechanisms for participation.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Critical Awareness</p> <p>The questions in this section benchmark the extent to which young people’s participation challenges power structures and whether practices critically examine systemic inequalities and recognise exclusions.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Recognition</p> <p>This section benchmarks the extent to which youth participation is recognised and accorded acknowledgement and respect.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Impact</p> <p>This section asks about how the practice affects actual policies in relevant organisations and benchmarks the extent to which the practice has a system for monitoring and documenting the impact of young people’s participation</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Youth Voice and Power</p> <p>The questions in this section allow users to benchmark the forms and spaces of their participation practice, young people’s inclusion in decision-making processes, the extent of young people’s agency, and the diversity of participation methods.</p>	

3 The logic and the operation of the calculator

3.1 The logic of the calculator

The calculator is based on criteria developed to assess inclusivity and intersectionality in participatory practices in deliverables D3.1 - D3.3. The user can choose to benchmark specific sections or all five of them. The calculator compares the users’ answers to an ideal case developed from the assessment criteria and provides the user with an inclusivity result based on the

comparison.

The user answers a series of questions by selecting yes/partially/no. All questions have a check box for a filter, “*This does not apply to my practice*”, that the user can select. The question is not calculated towards the user’s score if they check this box. The evaluation time depends on the number of sections the user wants to benchmark. The user can choose to benchmark any number of the five sections.

After answering all questions in the selected sections, the calculator provides a result page. On the result page, the user receives an overall inclusivity score based on all of their answers (**Overall Inclusivity Score**) and individual inclusivity scores for each section they have benchmarked (**Section Inclusivity Score**). There are four possible inclusivity levels in the calculator: *Getting started* (1), *Making progress* (2), *Moving forward* (3), and *Leading the way* (4). The four levels reflect the political and dynamic nature of intersectionality and inclusivity: there is always more to learn and strive for. More information about the calculation and the levels is provided in sections 3.2 through 3.4.

The calculator also provides suggestions for promoting inclusivity in deliberative and participatory practices across different contexts. The recommendations are formulated to be encouraging and educational. Users can utilise the recommendations to develop their participatory and deliberative practices in various areas.

3.2 Calculating inclusivity levels

All questions have three answer alternatives: “yes”, “partially”, and “no”. Each answer given to each question will be scored as 0, 50, or 100 based on the user’s answers. However, if the user selects the filtering question “*This does not apply to my practice*,” the question is excluded from their score calculation. The scores that each answer warrants in each question are presented in section 3.3.

A Section Inclusivity Score is calculated in the following way. In each section, the user’s total sum (determined by a simple addition of the scores the user’s answers warrant) is divided by the number of questions the user has answered in that section, excluding the questions the user has checked as “this does not apply to my practice”.

For example, in the section ‘Recognition’, with four questions, the Section Inclusivity Score is calculated in the following way (if the filtering question is not selected):

$$\text{(score in question 1 + score in question 2 + score in question 3 + score in question 4) / 4} \\ = \text{Section Inclusivity Score}$$

In a hypothetical situation where the user’s answers warrant the following scores

- Question 1: 0
- Question 2: 50
- Question 3: 50
- Question 4: 100

The user’s Section Inclusivity Score would be 50.

The user will receive as many Section Inclusivity Scores as the number of sections they have decided to benchmark.

The **Overall Inclusivity Score** is calculated in a similar manner: by dividing the user’s total sum (determined by simple addition) by the number of questions the user has answered, excluding those that the user has checked as “this does not apply to my practice”. This calculation is based on the total number of questions the user has answered in the calculator, dependent on the number of sections they chose to benchmark.

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In both instances, the user’s inclusivity score is thus a number between 0 and 100 (100: the maximum sum based on all questions the user has answered, divided by the total number of questions the user has answered). **The inclusivity score, however, is not presented to the user as a numerical value.** Instead, the results for each section are presented with a **corresponding level title and description**. In addition, **the Overall Inclusivity Score** is presented with a colour.

Depending on the user’s inclusivity score, they receive one of the following results: 0 = Level 1: Getting Started, 1-33 = Level 2: Making Progress, 34-66 = Level 3: Moving Forward, 67-100 = Level 4: Leading the Way.

Figure 2. Corresponding inclusivity scores and level titles

3.3 The questions and scores for each question

Table 1 displays all the questions in the calculator, along with the scoring for each question based on the user’s answer.

Table 1. The calculator questions and scores

Section: Inclusion			
In participant recruitment, are active efforts made to recruit those who would not typically participate?	✔ Yes: 100	✘ No: 0	Partially:50
Are participants recruited through self-selection, meaning they put themselves forward for participation?	✔ Yes: 0	✘ No: 100	Partially: 50
If people are recruited as representatives, do all of those who they will represent have the opportunity to (s)elect their representatives?	✔ Yes: 100	✘ No: 0	Partially: 50
Are efforts made to reach out to those young people with least access to participation and	✔ Yes: 100	✘ No: 0	Partially: 50

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Section: Inclusion			
encourage the participation of people with diverse gender, class, or sexual identities, (dis)abilities as well as different racial, ethnic, or migration backgrounds?			
Are spaces (physical or virtual) of participation accessible for those with additional needs, whether physical or mental?	✓ Yes: 100	✗ No: 0	Partially: 50
Is plain and accessible language used in recruitment and activities?	✓ Yes: 100	✗ No: 0	Partially: 50
Is participation in multiple languages possible, and is language interpretation available for those who need it in order to participate?	✓ Yes: 100	✗ No: 0	Partially: 50
Are all the costs of participation compensated for the participants?	✓ Yes: 100	✗ No: 0	Partially: 50
Is training provided to enable participation?	✓ Yes: 100	✗ No: 0	Partially: 50
Is the venue or space comfortable, welcoming and safe for all young people?	✓ Yes: 100	✗ No: 0	Partially: 50

Section: Youth Voice and Power			
Are young people co-designers or co-producers of the activities? This means engaging them in all stages of planning, development, and implementation of outcomes.	✓ Yes: 100	✗ No: 0	Partially: 50
Are digital technologies and/or social media employed to facilitate the participation of young people?	✓ Yes: 100	✗ No: 0	Partially: 50
Are young people able to participate in non-formal, everyday settings?	✓ Yes: 100	✗ No: 0	Partially: 50
If young people participate in formal sites, do these include places that would otherwise be hard for them to access (e.g., parliament and other institutions of power)?	✓ Yes: 100	✗ No: 0	Partially: 50
Is participation adult-led or adult-initiated?	✓ Yes: 0	✗ No: 100	Partially: 50
Can young people set the agenda by bringing their issues into discussion?	✓ Yes: 100	✗ No: 0	Partially: 50
Are young people seen mainly as subjects of democratic education rather than political or civic actors?	✓ Yes: 0	✗ No: 100	Partially: 50

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Section: Youth Voice and Power			
Are a wide range of voices heard in the participation process?	✔ Yes: 100	✘ No: 0	Partially: 50
Are facilitators or moderators employed to ensure equality in participation and/or mutual respect?	✔ Yes: 100	✘ No: 0	Partially: 50

Section: Critical Awareness			
Does the practice make visible societal power structures? For example, does it reveal norms related to race, colonial history, gender, social class, sexuality, ability, or age that reinforce existing hierarchies?	✔ Yes: 100	✘ No: 0	Partially: 50
Does the practice challenge power structures? For example, does it question norms related to race, colonial history, gender, social class, sexuality, ability, or age that reinforce existing hierarchies?	✔ Yes: 100	✘ No: 0	Partially: 50
Are participants encouraged to develop a shared understanding of a social phenomenon as problematic or unjust?	✔ Yes: 100	✘ No: 0	Partially: 50
Does the practice actively encourage learning from people in socially excluded positions?	✔ Yes: 100	✘ No: 0	Partially: 50
Does the practice aim to bring about institutional changes in public or political institutions, schools, and organisations?	✔ Yes: 100	✘ No: 0	Partially: 50
Does the practice aim to challenge injustice?	✔ Yes: 100	✘ No: 0	Partially: 50

Section: Recognition			
Is participation publicly acknowledged?	✔ Yes: 100	✘ No: 0	Partially: 50
Is participation remunerated (are participants paid)?	✔ Yes: 100	✘ No: 0	Partially: 50
Is participation recognised in a non-monetary way (e.g. accreditation, certification, awards, publicity)?	✔ Yes: 100	✘ No: 0	Partially: 50
If participants gain expert knowledge or training during the practice, is this knowledge or skill	✔ Yes: 100	✘ No: 0	Partially: 50

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Section: Recognition

accredited or certified?			
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Section: Impact

Do young people’s voices contribute to decision-making?	✔ Yes: 100	✘ No: 0	Partially:50
Are explicit recommendations made to achieve a policy impact?	✔ Yes: 100	✘ No: 0	Partially: 50
Is there a system for monitoring and evidencing the impact of the practice?	✔ Yes: 100	✘ No: 0	Partially: 50
Has the practice or project been formally assessed?	✔ Yes: 100	✘ No: 0	Partially: 50
Have the results of the assessment and the impact of policy recommendations been made publicly available?	✔ Yes: 100	✘ No: 0	Partially: 50

3.4 The inclusivity level descriptions

There are four possible inclusivity levels that the users can get depending on their inclusivity score. All levels have a corresponding level description, both for the Section Inclusivity Score and the Overall Inclusivity Score.

Level 1: Getting started

SECTION INCLUSIVITY SCORE: [SECTION NAME] is not yet a strong point in the practice. Click to see recommendations for how to improve [SECTION NAME].

OVERALL INCLUSIVITY SCORE: Inclusivity is not yet a priority in the practice. The current approach does not actively consider youth representation, recognition, or participation. The practice would benefit from a process of re-evaluating its structure, activities, and goals to enhance its capacity to include a wide range of young people and challenge existing power structures.

Level 2: Making progress

SECTION INCLUSIVITY SCORE: There is evidence that [section name] is considered in the practice but there is considerable room for further development. Click to see recommendations for how to improve [SECTION NAME] in the practice.

OVERALL INCLUSIVITY SCORE: The practice has some inclusive elements in place, but they are not yet comprehensive. There is still a lack of systematic efforts to ensure equity in youth participation.

Level 3: Moving forward

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SECTION INCLUSIVITY SCORE: The practice is on the right track with [SECTION NAME]. However, further efforts are needed to ensure that all barriers to inclusivity are fully addressed. Click to see recommendations for how to improve [SECTION NAME] in the practice.

OVERALL INCLUSIVITY SCORE: The practice has established a strong foundation for youth inclusivity. There are effective strategies in place, but some areas require further development to reach their full potential.

Level 4: Leading the way

SECTION INCLUSIVITY SCORE: Fantastic work! Inclusivity seems to be central in the practice in the section [SECTION NAME]. There is always more to learn. To continue improving, click to see recommendations for [SECTION NAME].

OVERALL INCLUSIVITY SCORE: Congratulations! The practice is highly inclusive, well-integrated into decision-making, and leads to tangible results. The practice actively promotes continuous learning and innovation in inclusivity. Share and promote these good practices throughout relevant communities.

4 Layout

Below are examples of the calculator layout. Figure 3 shows the calculator's first page, and Figure 4 shows the second page, examples of question pages and one example of a recommendations page.

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Figure 3. The first page

Figure 4. The second page, examples of question pages and a recommendation page

5 Technical description, data collection and privacy concerns

The partners at WeDo have been responsible for the programming and hold the copyright of the technical part of the calculator under CC BY-NC-ND 4.0 license.

Domain:

The calculator will be stored inside the actual SINCRONY website domain as an inside folder at <https://sincronyproject.eu/calculator>

Hosting/Server: Namecheap.

Programming Language: Questions are saved in a database (MySQL), loaded through PHP and JavaScript. Results are saved in session variables that are deleted after the session is over.

Data Storage:

The system is designed to prioritise user privacy. Users' data is not stored; only a session is open and closed each time, but there is no connection to the database. This means that no data is collected. Firstly, the questions are loaded from the actual section. Then, the selected values are summed following a division by the total number of questions to get the mean for the result.

Example of code:

```

11  $sql_data = "SELECT *,
12
13          (SELECT count(*)
14          FROM Questions q
15          WHERE q.Id_category = 1) as total_questions
16
17          FROM Questions
18          WHERE Id_category = 1
19          ORDER BY Position ASC LIMIT 1";
20  $connect_data = mysqli_query($con, $sql_data);
21  $result_data = mysqli_fetch_assoc($connect_data);
22  $total_questions = $result_data['total_questions'];
23
24  $score = 0;
25
26  $data_script = 1;
27  $noc = 0;
28  $answ = 0;
29  while ($data_script <= $total_questions){
30      $check_quest = "check-quest-".$data_script;
31      $quest = "question-".$data_script;
32      if(isset($_POST[$check_quest])){
33          $value = (int)$_POST[$quest];
34          $score = $score + $value;
35          $answ++;
36      }
37      else
38      {
39          $noc++;
40      }
41
42      $data_script++;
43  }
44
45  $media = $score / $answ;
46
47  $_SESSION['inclusion']['media'] = $media;
48

```

The calculator's privacy policy message:

Privacy policy

By clicking on the Footprint Calculator of the SINCRONY Project (<https://sincronyproject.eu/calculator>). I authorise WeDo Intelligence Made Easy S.L. (VAT number ESB67031849) to process my IP address for research purposes. My data will be processed in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data (General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR) and Organic Law 3/2018, of 5 December, on the Protection of Personal Data and Guarantee of Digital Rights (LOPDGDD).

This processed data, such as aggregated statistics and other non-personally identifiable information, may be shared with the other partners of the SINCRONY project for research or similar purposes. These aggregated statistics will not allow anyone to identify you.

Additional websites subject to the Privacy Policy

This Privacy Policy applies to the following websites and all associated subdomains:

- <https://sincronyproject.eu/calculator>
- <https://sincronyproject.eu/>

Processing of data

I may exercise my rights of access, rectification, cancellation, portability, restriction, opposition and withdrawal of consent at any time by sending an email to hola@wedoprojects.com, enclosing a document proving your identity.

Further information:

For more information, please see our Privacy Policy (<https://sincronyproject.eu/privacy-policy>) and Terms and Conditions of use (<https://sincronyproject.eu/terms-and-conditions>)

Last updated: 22 April 2025

6 Next steps

The calculator will be available for public use at www.sincronyproject.eu. It is available for use until the end of the SINCRONY project in June 2027. The calculator will be utilised in the SINCRONY project's WP5, "Piloting enhancement and innovation pathways."

The future extensions or existence of the inclusivity footprint calculator remain uncertain. Any extensions or the continued existence of the calculator after the project ends must be agreed upon separately. However, small changes to wordings and the calculations are permitted if user feedback warrants it. Additionally, translations of the calculator into languages other than English can be completed at this stage of the project in collaboration with project partners.